

SPIRITUALITY AND ENLIGHTENMENT, CULTURAL ISSUES WHICH ON TUZUK OF AMIR TEMUR

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Annotation: In the article " Temur tuzuklari " of the work historical importance and in it spirituality issues about thought reported .

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Our people spirituality again to upgrade attention being given the same at times spiritual perfection symbols has been of our ancestors left rich, spiritual from their heritage enjoy to be very important They are gems from the mines better , more unique , more valuable and incomparable are mines . Amir Temur spiritual potential the state office make , his internal and external policy designation with explained . of Movorounahr ancient economic , cultural fame recovery years his spiritual potential more maturity found and social in life in full manifestation it happened That's why for the country as well social of life all sides , state-idea system , economic and financial , agriculture , crafts , trade , culture , science, architecture , military issues , international relations , Islam religion , sharia and another fields to the goal according to developed .

Amir Temur himself set up reached great the state national and moral values relying on office did And this society justice , humanity criteria based on to manage in the country tranquility , peace , harmony preserved to stand take came Temur own hand under He is moral , polite , and especially fair among the leaders and generals to be Demand did He is in his " Tuzuk". of leaders fair to be society , state and the nation for how big important to the owner that it is showing gave

Amir Temur great state the charioteer and high to spirituality have be wise the ruler both political and spiritual in terms of very big historical important has These are : 1. Amir Temur in the 14th century country and interregional relationships by deepening economic to the space to combine movement did Integration work out Great silk the way past countries in the middle cultures environment starting from gave

2. Amir Temur state system and management organize in reaching to himself special school created , fair society decision in finding the law priority compliance did

3. Amir Temur statehood principles developed it intelligence potential , tactical and strategic based on formed .

4. Amir Temur kingdom spirituality and higher level to culture kneaded kingdom was ...

Temur and the Timurids period Medium Asia in culture separately period organize does Culture in history classic period calculated this period in particular , Uzbek of culture today's legal in the location basis being service does First of all , this period culture Temur basis put strong statehood principles based on formed socio-economic development with depends .

From history It is known that they were called Timurids dynasty From the 70s of the 14th century to the 16th century in Movaraunnahr , Afghanistan , Iran , Azerbaijan to their heads

rule does Timur and his descendants during In Turonzamin cultural in progress significant shifts happened gives

Owner Amir Temurin great kingdom very big and rich spiritual to the ground built , his of the state main column spirituality has been was Here it is that's it foundation Temur's " Temur in the work statement done " Temur rules". all events Amir Temur on behalf of story will be done . Amir Temurin in the play main doctrine - to society , socio-political to life view , united powerful feudal of the state political and moral principles expressed .

Author of Amir Temur's " Tuzuklar " . that confession which scientists the majority organize is enough These are among " Temur "laws". English translators and publishers Devi and Whites , popular Turk encyclopedia scientist Shamsuddin Sami , manuscripts big researcher NDMikluho There are also maclays . Other one group of scientists in his opinion , the work dates back to the 16th-17th centuries in India written

" Temur " - Amir Temur military and political from the activity information giver , his state structure and him manage private views statement done work

Amir Temur improvement , security and gray lands those who have mastered it to encourage big attention gave In particular , in the work " Ruin being lying down lands you have if so , then by prosperous let it be done, if the owner anyway, it 's fine to do neighbor if not enough , to him different tools and necessary things let them give it own place prosperous by doing take it Another commandment I did it, it 's broken being lying down in the lands we borrow damn it, it's broken bridges fix it, ditches and rivers on bridges Let them go on , har one to the address ropes let them build , " he said thoughts let's read " .

Amir Temur full respectively based on spiritual requirements , needs , principles relied on without that's it period spiritual culture development big trust with to emphasize that he looked need He is himself in his reign language , faith , traditions , regions differently has been of people solidarity too much for cares . of the world different from countries given thousands craftsmen the work with provides them between of relationships sincere to be attention gives " Temur in the "rules". many thoughts even now importance lost no The Timurids during created such unique spiritual legacies learning and preserve ours human it is our duty .

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